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Executive Summary of White Paper (5000 character limit)

The origin of galaxies is a fundamental research area in modern astronomy. Astronomers are now capable of surveying the stellar and gaseous content of galaxies from the first billion years after the Big Bang until the present day. The most pressing research questions in this field are: What role do galaxies play in reionizing the Universe? What are the key processes that galaxies undergo during their lifetimes, and how do these processes affect galaxy properties and scaling relations? The conditions under which galaxies evolve vary with cosmic time and environment. Analyzing photometric and spectroscopic observations of galaxies at early epochs and over a full range of local galaxy density is thus essential to paint a complete picture of galaxy evolution. This White Paper outlines the prospects for Canadian astronomers to unlock discoveries in this subject with upcoming facilities. Canada is well-positioned to tackle these outstanding science questions given the synergy between our rich telescope access and our broad expertise across the electromagnetic spectrum. As the field moves toward spatially resolved studies of distant galaxies and their environments, Canada has unique opportunities to make significant contributions in this area. In particular, we emphasize that remaining a partner in the TMT project, Euclid, JWST and Gemini are essential components of the future of distant galaxy studies in Canada.

Lead author and affiliation Allison Man, University of Toronto

Email address of lead author allison.man@dunlap.utoronto.ca

Other authors and affiliations

Roberto Abraham, University of Toronto
Rachael Alexandroff, University of Toronto
Raymond Carlberg, University of Toronto
Scott Chapman, NRC, Dalhousie University
Ivana Damjanov, Saint Mary's University
Julie Hlavacek-Larrondo, Université de Montréal
Adam Muzzin, York University
Laura Parker, McMaster University
Marcin Sawicki, Saint Mary's University
Suresh Sivanandam, University of Toronto
Tyrone E. Woods, NRC Herzberg

1 Introduction

The origin of galaxies is a fundamental research area in modern astronomy. Astronomers are now capable of surveying the stellar and gaseous content of galaxies from the first billion years after the Big Bang until the present day. The most pressing research questions in this field are: What role do galaxies play in reionizing the Universe? What are the key processes that galaxies undergo during their lifetimes, and how do these processes affect galaxy properties and scaling relations? The conditions under which galaxies evolve vary with cosmic time and environment. Analyzing photometric *and* spectroscopic observations of galaxies at early epochs and over a full range of local galaxy density is thus essential to paint a complete picture of galaxy evolution. This White Paper outlines the prospects for Canadian astronomers to unlock discoveries in this subject with upcoming facilities. Canada is well-positioned to tackle these outstanding science questions given the synergy between our rich telescope access and our broad expertise across the electromagnetic spectrum. As the field moves toward spatially resolved studies of distant galaxies and their environments, Canada has unique opportunities to make significant contributions in this area. In particular, we emphasize that remaining a partner in the TMT project, Euclid, JWST and Gemini are essential components of the future of distant galaxy studies in Canada.

2 Science Case: Reionization

2.1 The role of galaxies in reionizing the Universe

A major outstanding question in modern extragalactic research is how the Universe reionized. Hydrogen in the intergalactic medium is thought to be photo-ionized at $z \sim 7 - 10$ in a fairly rapid process (Planck Collaboration et al., 2016). The past decade has seen much progress in this field, particularly in discerning the relative importance of massive stars and quasars. However, as much progress has been made, we still have only about a hundred quasars, and only a handful of spectroscopically confirmed galaxies at $z > 7$ (e.g., Stark et al., 2017; Jung et al., 2019). These sparse observations suggest that massive stars provided most of the ionizing photons as quasars are too rare to fully reionize the Universe (Matsuoka et al., 2018). There remain, however, many questions to be addressed before we can fully characterize the reionization era. In particular, much larger samples of galaxies and quasars in the reionization epoch are needed, and higher signal-to-noise and higher spatial resolution observations are essential. With these larger samples we will pursue questions that include (but are not limited to):

- Which galaxies are the primary source of ionizing photons?
- What are the ionizing spectrum and the photon escape fraction of early galaxies?
- How did reionization progress over time on different spatial scales?

The luminosity function of galaxies at $z > 6$ is crucial for evaluating the cosmic star formation rate density budget, which in turn determines galaxy contribution to the production of escaping photons that can eventually reionize the intergalactic medium. The identification of galaxies at $z > 6$ is typically done with a spectroscopic follow-up of candidate galaxies with spectral energy distributions (SEDs) that exhibit strong Lyman break or of the systems with strong Lyman α emission line identified in narrow-band imaging. These features shift to near-infrared wavelengths at $z \gtrsim 7$, where atmospheric absorption becomes more severe than at optical wavelengths making ground-based spectroscopic observations more challenging. Even with the most sensitive NIR spectrographs on 8-metre class telescopes a secure detection, if at all possible, requires $\gtrsim 5 - 10$ hours of observations. The success rate of such spectroscopic confirmations are at present very low. Due to the sparsity of spectroscopic redshifts at $z \gtrsim 6$, galaxy luminosity functions in the first billion years are highly uncertain. Thus, present high- z luminosity distributions are based on unreliable and sometimes biased photometric redshifts.

2.2 Prospects in the 2020s

JWST will transform our understanding of reionization in the coming decade. Its unprecedented sensitivity over the 5-28 micron wavelength range will enable the detection of many galaxies throughout the epoch of reionization.

It will provide large samples of $z > 6$ galaxies with unprecedented constraints on the rest-frame UV and optical spectra. These measurements are crucial for an accurate characterization of the stellar populations of primeval galaxies, enabling us to infer the production rate of ionizing photons. A major breakthrough will be JWST’s access to a plethora of emission lines at high redshift: the ratios of Ly α to other UV lines such as He II, C III], and C IV, are important for discerning the nature of the ionizing source as well as the physical conditions of the ionized gas (density, ionization parameter, metallicity; [Feltre et al., 2016](#); [Hirschmann et al., 2019](#)). These line ratio diagnostics are particularly relevant for metal-poor galaxies that dominate the epoch of reionization, where heavy elements such as O and N are less abundant and traditional metallicity tracers based on those elements may not be reliable.

Millimeter spectral scans provides a complementary approach to spectroscopically identify dusty galaxies at $z > 6$ ([Strandet et al., 2017](#)). As spectral scans recently become a standard ALMA observing mode, ALMA is anticipated to routinely discover galaxies at the epoch of reionization that are too dusty to be detected even with JWST. Broadening the receiver bandwidth will improve the efficiency of spectral scans and is already the top priority of ALMA 2030 Development Roadmap¹. Furthermore, ALMA will constrain the warm ionized gas through far-infrared fine structure lines like [C II], [N II], and [O III] (e.g., [Laporte et al., 2019](#)). We anticipate a much better understanding of the interstellar medium of galaxies at $z > 6$ in the next decade, through a multi-wavelength approach that capitalizes JWST and ALMA synergy.

The TMT will revolutionize our knowledge of reionization in the next decade and beyond. The large collecting area of TMT is critically important to obtain detailed constraints on distant galaxies in ways that no other instruments can: IRIS will provide resolved kinematics of the warm ionized gas and stellar populations of galaxies at the epoch of reionization, chemical enrichment of Population III stars and the thermal history of the intergalactic medium from absorption lines along quasar sight-lines. Adaptive optics from NFIRAOS and resolved spectroscopy with IRIS at the TMT will enable a leap forward in our understanding on the physics of reionization.

The topology of the Universe contains complementary information on how the Universe was reionized. Intensity mapping experiments and the Square Kilometer Array² will complement the above facilities to provide a holistic picture of the reionization process.

3 Science Case: Galaxy assembly and evolution

Galaxy surveys in the past decade have radically improved our understanding of their formation and evolution. We now have a decent characterization of massive galaxies ($M_* > 10^{10} M_\odot$) at “cosmic noon” ($z = 1 - 3$). Massive galaxies have a rich diversity of stellar morphologies from irregular structure to disks and bulge-dominated systems (e.g., [Conselice, 2014](#)), and appear to have more turbulent kinematics than their present-day counterparts (e.g., [Wisnioski et al., 2019](#)). The number of distant galaxies with cold gas and dust mass measurements has drastically increased, providing insights into the conditions of star formation in these systems. Findings in the past decade have opened up many more new questions on the physics of galaxy evolution:

- What regulates star formation in galaxies?
- What drives the star formation history of the Universe?
- How do galaxy structure and kinematics evolve?

3.1 What regulates star formation in galaxies?

3.1.1 What promotes star formation?

Star formation in galaxies is regulated through the interplay between smooth gas accretion, galaxy mergers, and feedback processes. Galaxies at $z \gtrsim 2$ are known to deviate from local spiral galaxies on the Schmidt-Kennicutt

¹We refer to the White Paper on Development Priorities for ALMA (W019).

²We refer to the High-redshift 21cm Cosmology in Canada White Paper, the Line Intensity Mapping White Paper, and the SKA White Paper for a detailed discussion on this topic (W012, W038, W046).

relation (Kennicutt, 1998; Daddi et al., 2010; Genzel et al., 2010), a relation between cold gas densities and star formation rate densities. This discrepancy suggests that galaxies at $z \sim 2$ form stars more efficiently than the ones in the local volume. The mechanism responsible for the varying star formation efficiencies of galaxies with cosmic time is not well-understood.

Merging activity between galaxies can trigger starburst activity in nearby galaxies (Kartaltepe et al., 2010). The frequency of galaxy mergers and their effect on star formation are however less clear at $z \gtrsim 2$. Although massive galaxies have a higher incidence of companions at $z \sim 2$ than at $z \sim 0$ (Man et al., 2016), integral field spectroscopic (IFS) surveys of $z \sim 2$ massive star-forming galaxies show that most of them have disk-like rather than merger-like kinematics, as traced by their ionized gas emission (Wisnioski et al., 2019). Simulations have additionally shown that star formation in $z \sim 2$ massive galaxies are already so efficient that the effect of merger-enhancement is weak in comparison (Fensch et al., 2017). To understand how starburst activity is triggered at $z \sim 2$, we need higher spatial resolution observations of a larger and unbiased sample of galaxies. Most IFS surveys are impacted by beam-smearing due to seeing-limited resolution, and can underestimate the fraction of galaxies with merger-like kinematics. Critically missing are systematic studies of star formation efficiencies in $z \sim 2$ galaxies as it is currently too time-costly to obtain resolved maps of both molecular and ionized gas.

3.1.2 What suppresses star formation?

The observed growth of the galaxy “red sequence” implies that more and more massive galaxies quench their star formation over time, as they reach the end of their star formation episodes. The process by which galaxies quench their star formation remains a controversial subject in extragalactic research. Many physical mechanisms have been proposed in the literature (Man & Belli, 2018, and references therein). Feedback from active galactic nuclei (AGN) is the most commonly invoked explanation. Though supermassive black holes represent only a small fraction of the total mass of the host galaxy, their accretion is thought to provide sufficient energy to launch powerful winds (radiative feedback) and jets (mechanical feedback) and thus cause quenching of star formation. AGN feedback is typically invoked to suppress the formation rates of massive galaxies in cosmological simulations in order to match their observed abundances (e.g., Weinberger et al., 2018). In addition, the feedback processes may explain the tight relationships observed between the masses of supermassive black holes and the properties of their host galaxies (e.g., Ferrarese & Merritt, 2000). Aside from these negative feedback scenarios whereby AGN quenches star formation, positive AGN feedback has been suggested to enhance star formation through jet-induced or radiation pressure-induced gas compression (Ishibashi & Fabian, 2012; Silk, 2013). Despite much study, the exact details of AGN feedback remain the biggest unknown in extragalactic studies.

3.2 Cosmic star formation history

The cosmic star formation rate density quantifies the amount of star formation in galaxies over cosmic time. Its evolution traces the effects that cosmological-scale environment has on star formation within galaxies. Measuring the cosmic star formation density at $z > 6$ is fundamental to discern the role of galaxies in reionization, as discussed in Section 2. Rest-frame UV and far-infrared observations of galaxies are used as proxies for their star formation rates, whether unobscured or obscured by dust. Multi-wavelength galaxy surveys over the past decade have provided evidence that indicates the increase in star formation density from $z = 0$ to its peak at $z \sim 2$, and its decline thereafter at higher redshift (Madau & Dickinson, 2014). The evolution of cosmic star formation rate density mirrors that of the cosmic black hole accretion history, strengthening the argument that supermassive black-holes co-evolve with their host galaxies.

Although HST can currently sample the rest-frame UV emission of galaxies out to $z \sim 10$, the dust obscuration correction applied to convert the UV luminosity to the total star formation rate remains highly uncertain. The dust attenuation curve is known to vary with galaxy properties. It is important to obtain both UV and FIR observations of distant galaxies to correctly estimate their star formation rates. The main impediment to this is the lack of sensitivity in FIR survey instruments. In particular, Herschel telescope was not sufficiently sensitive to sample the dust thermal emission of low-mass, “normal” star-forming galaxies that are responsible for bulk of star formation

in the early Universe. Furthermore, it remains debated whether dusty galaxies could contribute significantly to the cosmic star formation rate density at $z > 3$ and whether they are currently unaccounted for in OIR surveys (e.g., [Casey et al., 2018](#)). Clearly, wide-field surveys of the rest-frame UV and FIR continuum for a statistical sample of galaxies out to the epoch of reionization are necessary for providing accurate constraints on the cosmic star formation rate density beyond $z > 3$.

3.3 Galaxy growth and assembly

Galaxies are thought to grow in mass through a two-phase process: in-situ star formation (Section [3.1](#)) proceeded by ex-situ accretion of mostly stars by mergers ([Oser et al., 2010](#)). As galaxies evolve on timescales of millions or even billions of years, astronomers must rely on scaling relations from large statistical samples to infer how galaxies evolve. We now have some constraints on various scaling relations at $z \sim 2$, enabled by multi-wavelength galaxy surveys. Stellar masses of galaxies appear correlated with their sizes, stellar velocity dispersions, ages, metallicities, and star formation rates (e.g., [Wuyts et al., 2011](#); [Toft et al., 2012](#); [Gallazzi et al., 2014](#); [van der Wel et al., 2014](#); [Sanders et al., 2018](#)). Any successful galaxy evolution model must be able to reproduce these scaling relations. The ultimate questions in understanding galaxy assembly are:

- What is the relative importance of in-situ star formation and ex-situ mass accretion by mergers in galaxy mass assembly?
- What role does the environment play in galaxy evolution?

3.3.1 Reconstructing formation histories

Chemical evolution is a clock for galaxy formation and evolution. Metals are created by fusion in the cores of stars, and get expelled to the interstellar medium in stellar winds and explosions. Galaxies therefore accumulate metals in the stars and interstellar medium as star formation progresses, resulting in a mass-metallicity relation. Different elements are synthesized by different types of stars. The elemental abundance is therefore a powerful probe of the star formation history of galaxies.

Although stellar metallicities in galaxies are well-measured out to $z = 0.7$ ([Gallazzi et al., 2014](#)), it has been challenging to detect the key Mg and Fe absorption features red-ward of rest-frame 5000\AA as they redshift into NIR wavelengths plagued by skylines. Only recently it has become feasible to constrain, for the first time, the stellar metallicity and abundance ratios of a bright $z \sim 2$ massive galaxy ($M_* > 10^{11} M_\odot$, [Kriek et al., 2016](#)), at an epoch immediately after it completed the bulk of its star formation. These single-object observations do not provide a clear view of how the most massive galaxies at $z > 2$ evolve into local giant ellipticals. Do they undergo a series of minor mergers with metal-poor satellites, or is their growth driven by a major merger with a companion of similar metal content? By comparing the metal content of statistical samples of $z > 2$ galaxies to their low-redshift counterparts, we can begin to reconstruct their chemical enrichment history and test various evolutionary scenarios.

The gas-phase metallicity of galaxies is a complementary tracer of their evolution history. Aside from probing metals synthesized during star formation, the gas metallicity is altered by gas inflows and outflows, by means of pristine gas accretion, galaxy interactions, and AGN- or starburst-driven outflows. Gas metallicity is typically traced by emission lines of the ionized gas across the electromagnetic spectrum. The gas-phase metallicity gradient is routinely measured in IFS surveys of local galaxies (e.g., [Belfiore et al., 2017](#)), but has only been measured in a few strongly lensed galaxies at $z \gtrsim 2$ due to the difficulty in resolving distant star-forming galaxies ([Jones et al., 2013](#)). The metallicity gradient of distant star-forming galaxies is thus fundamental in constraining galaxy formation processes.

3.3.2 The role of environment

Understanding the processes by which galaxies quench their star formation remains one of the most significant outstanding challenges for models of galaxy formation. Major studies in the last decade (e.g., [Peng et al., 2010](#)) have indicated that the physical processes causing quenching can be divided into two broad categories, one due

to secular processes most likely related to the mass of galaxies (mass quenching) and processes related to the environment of galaxies (environmental quenching). There is mounting evidence from studies of the local Universe that the physical process most likely responsible for environmental quenching is gas stripping. Ram-pressure from motion through the intra-cluster medium can remove substantial amounts of gas from a galaxy and potentially quench it on timescales of roughly the host halo dynamical time ($\sim 1\text{--}2$ Gyr).

Ram-pressure stripping events are just starting to be studied in large numbers in the nearby universe by IFS surveys with VLT/MUSE (Poggianti et al., 2017; Fossati et al., 2018). While it seems reasonable to implicate ram-pressure stripping as the dominant cause of environmental quenching, we have little information about this process. For example, the vast majority of galaxies in clusters and groups are quenched at the lookback time $\sim 5\text{--}10$ Gyr (e.g., Smith et al., 2012), when clusters were far less evolved, and galaxies had much higher gas fractions. Is the ram-pressure stripping seen in local clusters really analogous to the process that quenched the majority of cluster galaxies at $0.5 < z < 1.5$? Resolved $H\alpha$ observations of cluster galaxies and their surrounding medium are needed to test this.

3.4 Prospects in the 2020s

A coordinated, high resolution, multi-wavelength approach is key to address these questions. Spatially resolved NIR IFS observations, to trace ionized gas at $z \sim 2$, will increasingly become the tool of choice. In the early part of the decade JWST and GIRMOS will be at the forefront of a new era of IFS facilities capable of such high resolution, high sensitivity observations. Later in the decade much more powerful capabilities in light collecting power and angular resolution from TMT will follow. These upcoming facilities will shed new light on the effects of mergers and AGN on star formation, with the spatial resolution needed to accurately differentiate mergers from isolated disks and separate regions of the galaxy ionized by AGN, shocks or star formation. Large-area dense spectroscopic surveys in the optical and near-IR regime with Subaru PSF and MSE will unveil the connection between the evolution of large-scale structure and processes that drive the mass assembly and morphological transformation of galaxies from $z \sim 1 - 3$ to the present day. JWST/NIRCam and NIRISS will routinely detect $z > 4$ galaxies that are elusive with existing OIR instruments. JWST/NIRSpec will revolutionize the field by providing NIR spectra for statistical samples of massive galaxies with moderate spectral resolution, important to place constraints on their star formation history and initial mass function.

This will be leveraged to the fullest in conjunction with observations that trace the cold gas throughout galaxies (ALMA, ngVLA, SKA) as well as sensitive X-ray observations to probe the hot gas halos around galaxies (such as Lynx). A complete census of various gas phases is essential to characterize the phase transition of the outflowing gas, providing clues to constrain feedback models. Constraints on the star formation history and conditions of AGN-host galaxies through absorption line spectroscopy (with MSE and Subaru PFS) and molecular gas observations will shed light on the possible effects of the short-lived AGN activity on the potential for future star formation (e.g., Man et al., 2019). A powerful X-ray observatory will be necessary to conduct a complete census of AGN that will be able to span a range of luminosities and obscuration fractions. Finally, sensitive radio observations with next-generation facilities such as the SKA and ngVLA³ will allow us to probe the radio contributions from jets, winds and star formation at the faint-end of the radio luminosity function for a large sample of galaxies. These observational tests will become feasible in the next decade and are critically important for discerning various galaxy evolution models.

Deep wide-field NIR surveys such as the Euclid Deep Field and potential future JWST surveys will constrain the luminosity function of millions of galaxies at $z > 3$. Both telescopes will, for the first time, allow us to accurately measure the stellar masses of the galaxies that dominate the cosmic star formation rate budget at $z > 3$, to characterize the galaxy populations primarily responsible. Complementarily FIR/submillimeter surveys are needed to probe the abundance of dusty galaxies. FIR instruments⁴ more sensitive than Herschel is necessary to survey the dust continuum of large samples of distant galaxies.

³For more details, please refer to the white paper “Revealing the Origin and Cosmic Evolution of Supermassive Black Holes” (W034).

⁴A full discussion can be found in the White Paper on Science with Ground-based, Single-dish Submillimeter-wave Telescopes (E019).

4 Recommendations

Canada has more than three decades of experience in extragalactic research, with expertise across all sub-fields as well as instrumentation. Canadian extragalactic astronomers can readily access observing time with state-of-the-art telescope facilities across the electromagnetic spectrum. Investment in various facilities across all wavelengths will position Canada to unlock new scientific discoveries in the field in the 2020s and beyond. We summarize our key recommendations⁵ that can empower the Canadian community to maximize its impact in extragalactic research in the coming decade:

- An ELT facility is critical for a healthy development of the Canadian extragalactic community in the 2020s and beyond. Canada is currently committed to the TMT partnership. It is unclear whether Maunakea will be the ultimate site for the telescope. We strongly recommend continued participation in the TMT project on the basis of consensual cooperation with host communities⁶. If an agreement cannot be reached for the Maunakea site, a prompt decision on an alternative site is recommended. Other ELTs⁷ are being built, and without access to one, Canadian efforts in distant galaxies will surely be left behind.
- We recommend continued partnership in the JWST project which will provide unprecedented sensitivity at near- to mid-infrared wavelengths. In particular we note that continued funding support from the CSA for successful Canadian JWST observing proposals will be essential for maximizing Canadian output, competitiveness, and return on investment.
- Canada is already developing GIRMOS, which will be the first multi-object NIR integral field spectrograph with multi-conjugate adaptive optics capability. This is important because JWST/NIRSpec can only conduct IFS observations in single-object mode, making it inefficient for IFS surveys. We recommend the continued development of GIRMOS to enable NIR IFS surveys, and for leveraging its unique capability to pave way for future Canadian leadership for a second-generation TMT instrument.
- We recommend continued access to ALMA as it is indispensable for the FIR-submm synergy with JWST and TMT science.
- We support Canadian leadership and involvement in future single-dish submillimeter facilities like CCAT and SPICA⁸. There is already Canadian leadership in these projects and Canada would strongly benefit from participating in them.
- We recommend continued Canadian participation in Euclid⁹. The Euclid deep field science has the potential to make considerable impact on distant galaxy research. A larger Canadian team involved in this component would be beneficial to maximize scientific output.
- We recommend a leadership role in CASTOR¹⁰, a flagship Canadian mission that will address many science areas including that of galaxy evolution at $z \sim 1 - 3$ through morphological studies and in the context of large-scale structure.
- We recommend a leadership role in MSE¹¹, which will allow massive spectroscopic studies of galaxy evolution in the context of large-scale structure out to high redshifts.
- We recommend Canadian participation in Subaru¹², in part as a way to (re)build large-scale spectroscopic survey capacity in the community in preparation for MSE.

⁵The list of recommendations are *not* ranked by priority.

⁶We refer to the Maunakea Indigenous Rights White Paper (W008) for a relevant discussion.

⁷Opportunities are being pursued for Canadians to access the European ELT (e.g., CFI).

⁸We refer to the SPICA White Paper (W049) and the Mid- Through Far-Infrared Astronomy White Paper (W035) for further details.

⁹We refer to the Euclid White Paper (W020) for a full discussion.

¹⁰We refer to the CASTOR White Paper (W018) for a full discussion.

¹¹We refer to the MSE White Paper (W030) for a full discussion.

¹²We refer to the Canadian partnership with Subaru White Paper (W006) for a full discussion.

- It is essential to ensure that Canadian astronomers have sufficient personnel to handle and analyze the ever-growing surveys. Unlike the US and EU, Canada does not have funding schemes that enable astronomers to hire personnel for research projects. JWST projects will come with awards from the CSA, and we recommend that future telescope facilities to follow suit and budget for the human resources to facilitate science research.
- To fully capitalize the opportunities, it is to the advantage of the community to collaborate closely together to complement strengths and share resources.

1: How does the proposed initiative result in fundamental or transformational advances in our understanding of the Universe?

Understanding how galaxies form and evolve is a fundamental research area in modern astronomy. The proposed investigations represent the pathways to bring answers to long-standing questions with state-of-the-art facilities in the coming decade.

2: What are the main scientific risks and how will they be mitigated?

The complication of the TMT project remains the largest risk to the Canadian extragalactic research community. If the E-ELT and GMT projects proceed as planned, Canadian astronomers will be without access to a critical follow-up facility. TMT is essential for follow-up of targets detected with JWST and Euclid. Moreover, GIRMOS development puts Canadians in an excellent position to develop similar instrumentation for TMT. Without TMT such efforts and expertise could be squandered. There is no mitigation strategy here other than strong Canadian support for TMT, regardless of which site it is ultimately constructed on.

3: Is there the expectation of and capacity for Canadian scientific, technical or strategic leadership?

Yes. The proposed projects are well within the scientific and technical expertise of existing Canadian extragalactic astronomers. By investing in these facilities Canadian astronomers are expected to take on leadership roles in the projects. To fully capitalize the opportunities we recommend that human resources for scientific research to be made available in addition to investment in hardware.

4: Is there support from, involvement from, and coordination within the relevant Canadian community and more broadly?

Yes. This White Paper has highlighted a broad range of projects where the Canadian extragalactic community plays an active role. The proposed projects will encourage more collaborative efforts across institutes.

5: Will this program position Canadian astronomy for future opportunities and returns in 2020-2030 or beyond 2030?

Certainly! Canadian extragalactic astronomy is characterized by a collaborative environment and expertise across the electromagnetic spectrum. This White Paper presents a roadmap for Canadian astronomers to collaborate and to capitalize on the available facilities, to unlock transformational progress in galaxy evolution. Specifically the Canadian JWST Guaranteed Time Observations Programme, CANUCS, will provide a valuable dataset, as will the Euclid Deep Fields. Follow-up studies will be planned with other facilities such as ALMA, GIRMOS, and eventually TMT, providing plenty of opportunities for scientific discoveries in the next decade and beyond.

6: Is the cost-benefit ratio, including existing investments and future operating costs, favourable?

We refer to the respective instrument White Papers for a full discussion of the cost-benefit trade-off.

7: What are the main programmatic risks and how will they be mitigated?

There is a risk of delay in some facilities such as JWST and ELT. Ideally an ELT facility will be available before the end of the JWST mission which is expected to be launched in early 2021 (nominally 5 years, with a goal of 10 years). Canada is currently committed to the TMT project that is designed to be constructed on Maunakea. It is unclear, as of now, whether the TMT will proceed as planned. We recognize the importance to respect indigenous rights throughout the decision process. We recommend ACURA to inform and consult the astronomical Canadian community regarding the next steps and possible alternative sites, and to guarantee Canadian access to TMT or an equivalent facility by 2030.

8: Does the proposed initiative offer specific tangible benefits to Canadians, including but not limited to interdisciplinary research, industry opportunities, HQP training, EDI, outreach or education?

The science cases presented here require cutting-edge technical capabilities that Canadians can play scientific and technical leadership roles in. Canada's JWST contribution has been largely led by Canadian industry, which has provided direct economic benefits and capacity building for space instrumentation. Canada's leadership in TMT's NFIRAOS project has engaged several industrial partners across Canada in the optics and engineering design industries, helping them push their capabilities with such a complex instrument. Furthermore, this project is at the forefront of adaptive optics, which has been identified as a growth economic industry in the next decade. GIRMOS will also play a similar role, but on a shorter timescale. Our leadership in adaptive optics has trained several HQPs in the field of advanced control and optics who have gone on to be productive members in industrial and academic positions. Through these involvements Canada will continue to develop expertise in cutting-edge technologies and HQP in these areas.

The science proposed here is largely based on collecting large volumes of data and conducting careful statistical analysis. The skills required to this type of analysis are highly transferable. Being directly involved with the design and construction of these capabilities, Canadian HQP will have the added ability to fully utilize the scientific capabilities of these facilities.

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